

The Influence of Motivation, Voice Behavior and Work Engagement of the Individual Performance at Islamic Bank

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Abstract. This study discusses the problems frequently experienced by human resource managers in improving the performance of individual employees at Islamic banks. In this regard has been expressed by the fact that the need for human resources (HR) at Islamic banks much needed especially qualified individual performance. This study purpose to prove that the behavior of sound, employee engagement and motivation have an influence on the performance of the individual in Islamic banks. The method used is quantitative approach with a simple linear regression analysis to prove the independent variable (sound behavior, work engagement and motivation) have an influence on the dependent variable (performance of individuals). The sample used in this study is limited to the existing Islamic banks. The results of this study can be used as a reference for HR managers at companies, especially in the banking sector. For further research is expected to add to the object and the amount of sample, is not limited to only Islamic banks but coupled with commercial banks (conventional).

Keywords: individual performance, islamic bank, motivation, voice behavior, work engagement

Introduction

In the current era of globalization, economic syariah particularly regarding human resources in Islamic banks has become a concern in some of the discussions. In this regard has been expressed by the fact that the need for human resources (HR) at Islamic banks much needed. This phenomenon was sticking in some discussion because there are very few Islamic bank's human resources manager-level positions.

The establishment of Islamic bank in Indonesia very good response by Muslims, as Islamic banks have in its activities based on the Qur'an and the Hadis which are the basis and guidelines for Muslims in daily life. To disseminate Islamic banks does require seriousness for that is delivered is Islam that comes from divine revelation. Moreover, which resulted in the establishment of Islamic banking is the prohibition of usury, which in conventional banks are considered as

interest is defined as remuneration given by the bank based conventional principles to customers who buy or sell a product.

In a business entity, particularly in Islamic banks, management should treat their employees with fairness and attention to their needs. A leader with the ethics of treating employees fairly and consider their needs (Brown, 2005). Management such treatment can improve employee satisfaction and create trust, thus increasing employee motivation and can make the intensity of their performance (Cheng, 2014). Based on research conducted by Cheng et al. (2014) and Walumbwa (2011) stated in his research that ethical leadership affect job involvement, freedom and also the performance of employees in the work. Accordingly, the results of research conducted by previous researchers may explain the relationship between ethical leadership and collaboration with employees.

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The difference with previous research that this study is devoted to the company, especially the concept of Islamic banks. The previous study only examined based on ethical leadership as that of the conventional concept of the company (west). Therefore, the role of Islam is very important in every facet of life, especially business activities (tjajah).

Theoretical Review

Theory of Motivation

The theory of motivation can be grouped into two categories, namely the satisfaction theory (content theory) and the theory of the process (process theory). This theory is known as the concept of hygiene, whose scope is the content of the work (include accomplishments, work effort, recognition, work itself, responsibility and development potential of individuals) and hygiene factors, including salaries and wages, working conditions, policy administration business entities, the relationship between the individual, the quality of supervision (Maslow, 1943).

Ethical Leadership and Behavior Sound

Employee voice behavior is defined as behavior that emphasizes expression promotive constructive opposition intended to improve rather than just criticize (Dyne, 1998). Sound behavior is an important component of extra role behavior (Mayer, 2009).

Several studies have shown that ethical leadership is positively related to employee voice behavior, such as in research (Brown, 2005) noted that when employees feel that ethical leaders provide an environment of fair and highly moral, employees learn and explore the behavior of leaders, so that they are more likely to talk, report problems and offer suggestions for leaders.

Research conducted by Hoogh (2008) suggest that the ethical leaders encourage employees to express their opinions and eager to listen to their concerns. Thus, the behavior of the voice of facilitating employee.

Ethical Leadership and Job Involvement

Work engagement is considered as a unique motivation and conceptualized as the use of self-member organizations that play a role in their work in terms of physical, cognitive and emotional energy

(Rich, 2010). Research conducted by Zhu (2009) and Roberson (2010) shows that leadership is positively related to employee engagement. The leader is usually seen from how to play an important role in the process of social influence in an organization.

Literature Review

Research on the influence of motivation, behavior and involvement voice work on the performance of individual positive results. To support this, the author will present the results of previous research related to the management role of Islam on the performance of individual.

The study, positive results started to research conducted by Cheng (2014) in Taiwan. This study used a sample of 239 upper and lower level supervisors were obtained from a large economic research institute in Taiwan which gave a positive result to impact on the behavior of sound ethical leadership and job involvement, in this case the leaders motivate subordinates to be able to maximize their productivity.

Further research (Brown, 2005) is found that ethical leadership related to increased employee motivation and more positive work attitude. In a study conducted by the Kuhnelt (2009) and Salanova (2008) explained that the involvement of the work is the concept of motivation has a positive reference, meet each other, closely related to the positive thinking that is characterized by vigor, dedication and absorption. When employees exert high spirits and work with greater dedication and powerful for performing tasks, they tend to engage in behavior that is more altruistic and virtuous (Roberson, 2010) to improve and expand the perception and responsibilities relating to their work (Teh, 2012). In turn, employees are more likely to show a proactive employee voice behavior (Blader, 2009).

Work Motivation

One important aspect in the management of the company to maintain and improve morale in order to increase the productivity or performance of employees is to provide motivation for them. Robbins (2012) defines motivation as a willingness to issue a high-level effort to organizational objectives are conditioned by the ability to meet an individual need. Employee morale is needed in a business entity, as with morale high employee, the employee may issue

its ability as much as possible in order to realize the objectives together.

Based on research conducted by Maulani (2003) stating that motivation was positively related to labor productivity or performance, the higher the motivation variable, the higher employee productivity. In his research, Darmanwansyah (2012) stated that there is a positive relationship between work motivation (incentives, working conditions) to the performance of civil servants, so the authors propose the following hypothesis:

H1: Work Motivation positive effect on the performance of individual

Voice Behavior

Based on research conducted by Dyne (1998), Mayer (2009) and Brown (2005), sound behavior in a company can be a positive influence on the performance of individual employees. Sound behavior is here defined as "behavior which emphasizes the promotion of constructive challenge expressions which are intended to improve not just criticize". Sound behavior is an important component of the additional role behavior.

Company leaders are advised to be able to encourage their employees to express their opinion and listen to complaints passionate employees, thereby facilitating employee voice behavior (Hoogh, 2008). Based on the explanation of the behavior of the voice, the authors propose the following hypothesis:

H2: Behavior sound positive influence on the performance of individuals within the company

Work Engagement

Work engagement is considered as a unique motivation and conceptualized as avail themselves members of the organization for their job role in terms of physical, cognitive and emotional energy, so that the work engagement positively affects the performance of individuals (Rich, 2010). In another study found that leadership is positively related to job involvement (Zhu, 2009).

Research conducted by Roberson (2010) about the employee shows that leadership is positively related to employee engagement. Leadership here is intended how top-level management as well as lower levels can work together to engage in any activities of the employee's job, pay attention to things about what is or what has been done by employees, so with the

involvement of such work is expected to improve employee performance.

Several studies have used social learning perspective to explain how leaders influence employee engagement. If the ethical leaders dedicated themselves in work engagement and sound behavior, based on social learning perspective, employees learn and emulate the example of the role of interesting behavior, it will be able to generate motivation and energy in their work. For that, the authors propose the following hypothesis:

H3: Work engagement positively affects the performance of individuals

Fig. 1. Model Research

Research Methods

Types and Sources of Data

This study uses the data type of research using a quantitative approach. Research methods with quantitative approach is a form of research that is based on data collected during systematic research of the facts and the properties of the object to be studied. The reason the author chose quantitatively in this study, because the source of the data used is derived from the primary data in the form of direct interviews with the object of research using questionnaires.

Research Instruments

Research instrument is a tool to obtain or collect data to be processed. Instruments in this study using questionnaires. The author uses a questionnaire with researchers previously (Cheng, 2014), however there are some reductions because the author only took only two variables in the questionnaire. Before the questionnaires were distributed, the researchers also had to test the validity and reliability which refers to

earlier research (Cheng, 2014) which has a variable sound behavior and job involvement in the questionnaire and which have variable work motivation (Putra, 2013).

Scaling method used in this study is the instrument with a Likert scale type scale interval (Hartono, 2015). The scale of the researchers used to measure the responses of research subjects to questions in the questionnaire with a five-point scale that is Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Less Agree (LA), Disagree (DA), and Strongly Disagree (SDA).

Location and Object Research

Researchers will conduct research on existing Islamic banks in Batam. Researchers chose the research object because of the development of Islamic banks in Batam experienced significant progress in line with the growing public awareness of the importance of Muslim sharia principles in everyday life. Researchers obtain data research using primary data through questionnaires distributed to the employees who work on Islamic banks in Batam.

Sample Size Determination Techniques

The population of the writer used in this study were employees or staff who are still actively working on Islamic banks in Batam. Researchers are not sure how many populations to be studied because data on the number of employees by the bank strictly confidential. In determining the amount of the population in this study the authors use the formula Slovin. Slovin formula used to determine the number of samples in a study (Setiawan, 2007). The Formula Slovin as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1+d^2 N}$$

n = sample; N = population; d = the alleged error or significance = 0.05

Then the number of samples in this study is:

$$n = 285 / (1 + 0.05^2 * 285)$$

$$n = 285 / 1.7125$$

$$n = 166.42336 = 166 \text{ employees}$$

In this study, the research method to be used is non-probability sampling method is nonrandom sample selection, which means that not all elements have the same opportunity to be selected as sample. The samples in this study using purposive sampling

technique. Such sampling is done by taking a sample of a population based on a certain criteria based on considerations of researchers (Hartono, 2015). The criteria that the authors specify that Islamic bank employees who are still working in 2016.

Results and Discussion

The object of research used by researchers is the Islamic banks by using a sample of employees or staff who are still working in 2016. Based on these criteria, samples that can be used by investigators in this research were 180 respondents.

Table 1

Characteristics of Data	
Description	Total
Questionnaires Distributed	200
Questionnaires were distributed	180
Questionnaire were not filled respondent	20
Questionnaire which can be sampled	180
Data outlier	0
Total sample	180

Respondents who have filled out a questionnaire study then identified based on gender. This identification of research done to determine the general characteristics of respondents.

Table 2

Characteristics of Respondents		
Gender	Frequency (person)	Percentage (%)
Man	118	65.6
Woman	62	34.4
Total	180	100.0

The 180 respondents who filled out the questionnaire, it appears that the number of male respondents more than female respondents with a difference 31.2%.

Testing Instruments

Testing instrument against indicators of each variable in order to know the level of valid and reliable indicator as a measuring tool. This instrument consists of testing the validity and reliability test.

Validity test used to measure whether or not a legitimate or valid questionnaires. Researchers conducted a test by finding the correlation between scores of each item questions with a total score of each dimension. A questionnaire considered valid if $r_{\text{count}} > r_{\text{table}}$ (Ghozali, 2012).

Table 3
Validity Test

Variable	Item	Validity		Conclusion
		r count	r table	
Voice Behavior	Q1	1.000	0.1230	Valid
	Q2	0.536		Valid
	Q3	0.561		Valid
	Q4	0.459		Valid
	Q5	0.433		Valid
	Q6	0.460		Valid
Work Engagement	Q7	0.235	0.1230	Valid
	Q8	0.154		Valid
	Q9	0.206		Valid
	Q10	0.125		Valid
	Q11	0.200		Valid
	Q12	0.129		Valid
Work Motivation	Q13	0.153	0.1230	Valid
	Q14	0.231		Valid
	Q15	0.262		Valid
	Q16	0.149		Valid
	Q17	0.253		Valid
Employee Performance	Q18	0.150	0.1230	Valid
	Q19	0.348		Valid
	Q20	0.237		Valid
	Q21	0.190		Valid

Each indicator question used by researchers to have r count larger than r table, which means that the indicator questions from each of the variables that researchers use in this study is valid to be used as a measurement variable.

Reliability is a tool to measure the reliability or reliable a questionnaire if the response to a statement consistent or stable over time. Components of the questions in the questionnaire is considered reliable and consistent with the variables in a study if it gives Cronbach alpha values. A research instruments can be declared reliable if the reliability coefficient (Cronbach alpha value) is greater than 0.60 (Ghozali, 2012).

Table 4
Reliabilities Test

Model	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
X1_Voice Behavior	0.887	1.127
X2_Work Engagement	0.863	1.159
X3_Motivation	0.884	1.131

All variables has a Cronbach alpha value greater than the default value, 0.60. Thus, it can be concluded that all the variables that researchers use in this study is reliable.

Classic Assumption Test

Normality test purposed to test whether there is a variable in the regression model residuals have the

normal distribution. This normality test can be performed on multiple linear regression test that can be seen on the histogram charts and diagrams P-P Plot. In this test, the decision-making criteria is if a curved curve in diagram form the arch histogram normal curve and also the P-P diagram shows plots Plot to follow the straight line, then the residual otherwise normal and normality assumptions are met (Hidayat, 2013).

Fig. 2. P-Plot Diagram

The arch curves at P-P diagram shows plots Plot to follow the straight line, it can be concluded that the data were normally distributed residuals and normality assumptions are met.

Table 5
Multicollinearity Test

Variable	Total Item	Reliability		Conclusion
		Alpha Cronbach	Standard	
Voice Behavior	6	0.896	0.60	Reliable
Work Engagement	7	0.893	0.60	Reliable
Work Motivation	4	0.896	0.60	Reliable
Employee Performance	4	0.893	0.60	Reliable

The data obtained from the sample there are no statistics multicollinearity because the amount of tolerance is quite high with the average value (0.878) from the value of 0.10 and VIF (variance inflation factor) to conduct voice, involvement work and work motivation (X1, X2, X3) respectively 1.127, 1.159 and 1.131 also showed none of the independent variables that have a value of more than 10 (0.10). So we can conclude that there is no multicollinearity between independent variables. Terms to avoid multicollinearities is the tolerance value should not be

less than 0.10 and VIF must not be 10 (0.10) (Ghozali, 2012).

Heteroscedasticity test aims to test the occurrence of inequality or the difference in residual variance of the observations by the observations of others. Researchers conducted the testing heteroscedasticity with glejser test by way of regressing the absolute value of the residuals of the independent variables. A good regression model in a study is not going heteroscedasticity if an independent variable has a significance value of correlation > 0.05 (Ghozali, 2012).

Table 6
Heteroscedasticity Test

Variable	Sig.	Description
Voice Behavior	0.887	No heteroscedasticity
Work Engagement	0.863	No heteroscedasticity
Work Motivation	0.884	No heteroscedasticity

All independent variables have significance value above the standard value of 0.05 indicating that all independent variables nothing significant in influencing the dependent variable, it can be concluded that there is no heteroscedasticity on data.

Hypothesis Test

The method I use to test the hypothesis in this study is a simple linear regression statistical T - test (partial). Statistical T-test was conducted to determine the effect of each independent variable partially.

Table 7
Hypothesis Test with T-Test

Model	T	Sig.
1 (Constant)	5.985	0.000
X1_Voice Behavior	1.514	0.132
X2_Work Engagement	1.431	0.154
X3_Motivation	3.866	0.000

The results of the t test for sound behavioral variables, work engagement and motivation are 1.514, 1.431 and 3.866 with a significance value of each is 0.132, 0.154 and 0.000, so it can be concluded that H1 voice behavior, T arithmetic $<$ T table (1,514 $<$ 1,65346) and the significance value calculated $>$ significance standard (0,132 $>$ 0,05). H2 work engagement, T arithmetic $<$ T table (1,431 $<$ 1.65346) and the significance value calculated $>$ significance standard (1,154 $>$ 0.05). H3 work motivation, T arithmetic $>$ T table (3,886 $>$ 1.65346) and the significance value count $<$ significance standard.

Simple Linear Regression Analysis

Simple linear regression analysis is an analysis of the linear relationship between two or more independent variables (X) to the dependent variable (Y).

Table 8
Simple Linear Regression Testing

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	
	B	T
1 (Constant)	10.794	5.985
X1_voice behavior	0.168	1.514
X2_work engagement	0.086	1.431
X3_Motivation	0.302	3.866

The regression equation as follows:

$$Y = a + b_1 * X_1 + b_n * X_n$$

$$IP = a + b_1 * MK + b_2 * PS + b_3 * KK + e$$

$$IP = 10.794 + 1.514 + 1.431 * 3.866 + e$$

IP = Individual Performance;

WM = Work Motivation;

VB = Voice Behavior;

WE = Work Engagement;

e= standard error

Constant value of (10.794), the value of positive constants show the positive influence of the independent variable (voice behavior, work engagement and motivation). When the independent variable goes up, then the individual performance variable (Y) will go up.

Regression coefficients voice behavior (X1) is 0.168 or 16.8%, it means that if the voice behavior increase unit, then individual performance (Y) will be increased by 0.168 or 16.8%. Based on calculations, it is known that the value of the coefficient T count is smaller than the value of the coefficient T table (1.514 $<$ 1.65346), it can be concluded that the variable voice behavior (X1) has no effect on the individual performance. The regression equation $Y = 10.794 + 0.168 + e$.

Regression coefficients work engagement (X2) that is equal 0.086 (8.6%), meaning that if the variable work engagement increased unit, then individual performance variable (Y) will increase by 0.086 (8.6%). Based on the calculations, it is known that the value of the coefficient T table (1.431 $<$ 1.65346), it can be concluded that work engagement variables (X2) has no effect on the individual performance (Y). The regression equation $Y = 10.794 + 0.086 + e$.

Regression coefficient value variable work motivation (X3) that is equal 0.302 (30.2%), meaning that if the work motivation increased unit, then individual performance variable (Y) will increase by 0.232 (23.2%). Based on calculations, it is known that the value of the coefficient T table ($3.866 > 1.65346$), it can be concluded that work motivation has a positive influence on the individual performance (Y). The regression equation $Y = 10,794 + 0,302 + e$.

Data Analysis

Based on statistical tests that have been described, it can be concluded that the noise behavior has no effect on the performance of the individual or the hypothesis is rejected. This is because $T \text{ arithmetic} < T \text{ table}$ ($1.514 < 1.65346$) and the significance value calculated $>$ significance standard ($1.132 > 0.05$), while the requirement for the hypothesis is accepted if T is bigger than T table and a significance value smaller count or equal to the value of the standard significance (Raharjo, 2015). This study is not in line with previous studies conducted by Dyne (1998), Mayer (2009), Brown (2005), Hoogh (2008), Dyne (1998), Mayer (2009), Brown (2005) and Hoogh (2008).

Based on statistical tests that have been explained, it can be concluded that the involvement of labor has no effect on the performance of the individual or the hypothesis is rejected. This is because since $T \text{ arithmetic} < T \text{ table}$ ($1.431 < 1.65346$) and the significance value calculated $>$ significance standard ($0.154 > 0.05$). This research is not in line with research conducted by Rich (2010), Zhu (2009), and Roberson (2010).

Based on statistical tests that have been described, it can be concluded that motivation (motivation) positive effect on the performance of the individual or the hypothesis is accepted. This is because $T \text{ arithmetic} > T \text{ table}$ ($3.866 > 1.230$) and a significant value count $<$ significance standard ($0.000 < 0.05$). In the Islamic banks, one important aspect in the management of the company to maintain and improve morale in order to increase the productivity or performance of employees is to provide motivation for them. This study are consistent with previous studies conducted by Robbins (2012), Maulani (2003), and Darmanwansyah (2012). One important aspect in the management of the company to maintain and improve morale in order to increase the productivity or performance of employees is to provide motivation for them.

Conclusion

This study has a model to test the effect of sound behavior, work engagement and motivation on the performance of individual Islamic bank in the city of Batam. Based on these test results, it can be concluded that Voice behavior does not have a significant effect on the individual performance. Work engagement had no effect on the performance of the individual (employee). Job involvement here means the bank management does not necessarily involve its employees in every activity of the company, only certain employees are involved. Work motivation positive influence on employee performance. With high morale (high motivation), the employee may issue its ability as much as possible in order to realize the goals together.

Implication

This study examined the effect of sound behavior, work engagement and work motivation on employee performance. From this study it can be concluded that the performance of the individual (employee) can increase if the work motivation can be fulfilled to the employee. The results could be useful for managers of human resources (HR) banking and non-banking company as a reference in maintaining the performance of individual employees to the company's survival. Individual performance can maximize employee productivity that can support the survival and ideals of the company.

Limitation

Based on the above conclusions, while the natural limitations that researchers. Companies that used in this study is limited to the banking sector, especially in the Islamic bank. There are several questionnaires that were rejected by one of the banks studied sariah. There are some Islamic bank employees or staff who may fill out a questionnaire does not fit the circumstances, so there is some inaccurate data. During the study, researchers found there were several employees or staff who are doing office tasks that must be resolved, so that was not optimal in answering questions. Complicating the proposed permit researchers to the Islamic bank which is the object of research. This is because the parties wish the researchers made the object of research is not their memorandum of understanding (MoU) with the campus.

References

- Blader, S. A. (2009). Testing and Expanding the Group Engagement Model. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 445-464.
- Brown, T. L. (2005). Ethical Leadership: A Social Learning Perspective for Construct Development and Testing. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Process*, 117-134.
- Cheng, J. W. (2014). Ethical Leadership, Work Engagement and Voice Behavior. *Industrial Management and Data Systems*, 3.
- Darmanwansyah, A. H. (2012). Analisis Motivasi Kerja Pegawai di Kantor Dinas Kesehatan Kabupaten Sidrap. Sidrap, FKM-Unhas Makassar.
- Dyne, V. (1998). Helping and Voice Extra-Role Behaviors: Evidence of Construct and Predictive Validity. *Academy of Management Journal*, 108-119.
- Ghozali, I. (2012). *Aplikasi Analisis Multivariate dengan Program IBM SPSS 20*. Semarang: IBM Corporation.
- Hartono, J. (2015). *Metodologi Penelitian Bisnis*. Yogyakarta: BPF E Fakultas Ekonomika dan Bisnis UGM.
- Hoogh, D. A. (2008). Ethical and Despotism Leadership Relationships with Leader's Social Responsibility, Top Management Team Effectiveness and Subordinates Optimism: A Multi Method Study. *Leadership quarterly*, 297-311.
- Kuhnel, J. S. (2009). Does Work Engagement Increase after a Short Respite? *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 575-594.
- Maslow, A. (1943). *Motivation Theory*. New York, United States of America: Ppm.
- Maulani, R. (2003). Pengaruh Motivasi Kerja Terhadap Peningkatan Produktivitas Kerja Karyawan Berdasarkan Persepsi Karyawan Pada Dinas Pendapatan Provinsi Jawa Barat. Bandung: Universitas Widyatama.
- Mayer, D. k. (2009). How Low Does Ethical Leadership Flow? Test of a Trickle-Down Model. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Process*, 1-13.
- Putra, R. (2013). Pengaruh Kepemimpinan dan Motivasi Kerja terhadap Kinerja Karyawan PT Bank Syariah Mandiri Cabang Petisah. Medan: Universitas Sumatera Utara.
- Rich, B. L. (2010). Job Engagement: Antecedents and Effects on Job Performance. *Academy of Management Journal*, 617-635.
- Robbins, S. P. (2012). *Organizational Behavior*. New Jersey, United States of America: Pearson Education, Inc.
- Roberson, M. B. (2010). The Relationship between Charismatic Leadership, Work Engagement and Organizational Citizenship Behaviors. *The Journal of Psychological*, 313-326.
- Salanova, M. A. (2008). A Cross-National Study of Work Engagement as a Mediator between Job Resources and Proactive Behavior. *The International Journal of Human Resources Management*, 116-131.
- Setiawan, N. (2007). *Penentuan Ukuran Sampel Memakai Rumus Slovin dan Tabel Krejcie-Morgan*. Bandung: Fakultas Peternakan Universitas Padjadjaran.
- Teh, P. A. (2012). Knowledge Sharing, Job Attitudes and Organizational Citizenship Behavior. *Industrial Management & Data Systems*, 64-82.
- Walumbwa, J. A. (2011). When Leadership goes Unnoticed: The Moderating Role of Follower Self-Esteem on the Relationship between Ethical Leadership and Follower Behavior. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 573-582.
- Zhu, B. W. (2009). Moderating Role of Follower Characteristics with Transformational Leadership and Follower Work Engagement. *Group and Organization Management*, 590-619.